

INTELLIGENT DECISION SUPPORT FOR PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE PLANNING OF EQUIPMENT IN THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY

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Abstract. This article discusses the relevance of intelligent decision support systems in the preventive maintenance of equipment at chemical industry enterprises, particularly when planning maintenance and repair activities. It summarizes the experience of implementing intelligent decision support in maintenance planning across various industries, examines the challenges faced by the enterprise under study, and highlights the issue of preparing data for intelligent support algorithms. These algorithms are based on repair logs and equipment inspection records filled out by expert specialists. The article sets out the tasks and solutions for addressing these challenges, considering the restrictions at the studied enterprise. The results of applying methods to prepare expert data for algorithm operation are presented, along with an assessment of their impact on improving equipment technical condition by enhancing the accuracy of maintenance planning. The article concludes by affirming the feasibility of using intelligent decision support based on expert data for planning preventive maintenance activities at chemical industry enterprises.

Keywords: Preventive maintenance of equipment; intelligent decision support; planning systems; data processing.

INTRODUCTION

Preventive maintenance, as a proactive approach to the manifestation of equipment failures, is aimed at preventing faults through systematic planning and the execution of maintenance and repair activities [1]. Preventive maintenance can significantly increase the lifespan of equipment and improve operational safety, especially in industries such as chemical manufacturing, where the reliability of equipment and safety of processes are of utmost importance [2]. Research in areas such as intelligent decision support for preventive maintenance of equipment largely focuses on the application of advanced machine learning algorithms and data analytics, which allow optimization of decisions based on data collected directly from equipment. I. Yasini and N. Kurniati, in their work, argue that the more data that can be collected, the more accurate the probability of unplanned downtime can be assessed. By gathering operational data from various sources, performing multidimensional clustering, and identifying deviations, a comprehensive understanding of the real condition of equipment can be achieved, which in turn increases the efficiency of planning proactive actions [3]. Yan Li and co-authors propose dynamic maintenance, which combines predictive

group maintenance with unplanned opportunistic maintenance over an infinite time horizon. This approach removes the limitations of traditional models, which often rely on fixed intervals between repairs. According to the authors, this policy is focused on obtaining real-time data about the equipment's condition through dynamically updated information on its technical status and maintenance results, allowing the maintenance planning system to respond to changes [4]. S. Gupta and co-authors conclude that most research in this field is focused on systems equipped with monitoring and diagnostics tools, assuming that the entire fleet of equipment in the enterprise is covered by such tools, and that real-time data is readily available for use in decision-support algorithms [5].

Recognizing the importance of intelligent decision support in preventive maintenance planning, it should be noted that its implementation in the specific conditions of an industrial enterprise may be accompanied by several challenges. One such problem is the economic inefficiency of equipping the entire equipment fleet with complex sensor systems. Indeed, sensors that collect real-time data can provide valuable information about critical assets, but installing such sensors across the entire fleet of equipment may be prohibitively expensive and technically challenging. Therefore, a hybrid approach to data acquisition should be considered, in which sensors are installed only on critical equipment, while relying on regular inspection records made by qualified personnel for the rest of the equipment. This approach allows intelligent decision support systems to use heterogeneous data sources [6] and subsequently optimize preventive maintenance planning. However, this requires preliminary data preparation, as inspection and maintenance information recorded by expert specialists in logs is often in unstructured text form. To transform text data into structured formats suitable for analysis and inclusion in planning algorithms, effective data transformation methods are needed.

Given that only part of the existing equipment at the researched enterprise is equipped with sensors, and the data from these sensors are highly suitable for use by information systems, the task is to collect data from the remaining equipment, including descriptions of inspection results, for use in a prognostic model in the context of equipment operating conditions for intelligent decision support in planning preventive actions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An important aspect of decision support in preventive maintenance planning, based on a hybrid data acquisition approach, is the ability to transform unstructured data from various text records into a structured format and incorporate this data into the overall expert knowledge base, which provides an understanding of the operational conditions of equipment maintenance. The general characteristics of the structure of such a knowledge base are presented in **Table 1**.

Advances in natural language processing (NLP) and intelligent text analysis enable the transformation of expert-provided data into structured datasets, which can then be analyzed alongside sensor data. Methods for transforming data obtained from text descriptions into a structure suitable for use in decision-making algorithms are presented in **Table 2**.

Table 1. General characteristics of the expert knowledge base structure.

Type of Data	Characteristics
Identification Data of Equipment	Information that uniquely identifies the equipment, such as name, designation, model, serial number, etc.
Operating Modes	Descriptions of various modes in which the equipment can operate, such as normal operation modes, standby modes, emergency operation modes.
Passport Characteristics	Regulatory service life, service cycles, calculated loads, specifications for parts and components, specifications for consumables.
Operational Parameters	Descriptions of various parameters that need to be monitored during operation, such as temperature, pressure, flow rate, etc.
Maintenance Procedures	Composition and descriptions of recommended maintenance procedures for the equipment, including schedules for regular inspections, lubrication requirements, cleaning procedures.
Typical Defects and Failures	Descriptions of known defects and failures, possible methods for their elimination.
Typical Operating Violations	Descriptions of personnel errors, typical violations in the equipment operation process.
Inspection Records	Descriptions of inspection results, identified issues, recorded violations, checks of operational parameters.
Maintenance Records	Descriptions of all maintenance work performed on the equipment, including dates, detailed information on completed work, and replaced parts.

Table 2. Methods for transforming text data.

Methods	Characteristics of Methods
Data Collection and Preprocessing	Data source initialization. Text cleaning.
	Data enrichment.
	Data augmentation
NLP for Text Representation and Analysis	Tokenization, "Bag of Words" (BoW), TF-IDF. Word embeddings, Contextual embeddings. Named Entity Recognition (NER). Topic modeling.
Clustering Defects and Violations	K-means clustering. Hierarchical clustering.
Predictive Maintenance Recommendation Model	Logistic regression. Random forest. Gradient boosting. Performance metrics and model validation. Risk assessment.
Metrics and Model Validation	Predictive Model Verification. metrics Validation.

Data on the results of inspections are collected from inspection logs filled out by specialists. These data are represented in the maintenance and repair management information system as textual descriptions. Before training the model, the textual data

undergo several preprocessing steps. In particular, tokenization and standardization methods are applied to ensure text uniformity, including the removal of extraneous symbols, punctuation, followed by normalization of lowercase letters. To reduce data variability, it is important that domain-specific terminology, including abbreviations and synonyms, is standardized.

As an example, consider textual descriptions of the results of inspections of maintenance objects such as valves. Valves differ in types, and for each valve type, there is documentation on repairs and maintenance, which can also be used as a data source to describe the operating and maintenance context. For example, from the section "List of possible malfunctions and methods of their elimination" in the "Valve Maintenance Manual," we extract defect characteristics, as well as key terms, actions, and conditions related to their repair and maintenance. Then, using tokenization and lemmatization, we clean the collected data. As a result of the cleaning process, terms such as "inspection," "replace," and "tightness" will be identified.

Next, the results of the inspections are processed. Continuing with the example of the valve, consider an inspection result description as follows: "As a result of the valve inspection, a tightness violation of the ring was detected, and traces of liquid leakage from under the ring were found." This text contains important information about the type of defect (tightness of the sealing ring) and observed symptoms (liquid leakage). This text is cleaned by removing non-informative words and irrelevant punctuation so that only meaningful data remain. In the text above, phrases such as "as a result of the inspection" and conjunctions should be filtered out so that focus is placed on the specific conclusions: "tightness defect of the rings, traces of liquid leakage." Standardization of terminology can also be applied here to ensure uniformity. For example, terms such as "tightness violation" and "liquid leakage" are normalized across all records and brought to formulations like "tightness defect," "liquid leak."

Further preprocessing of inspection results involves tokenizing each text, breaking complex phrases into individual words and components, and applying lemmatization to reduce words to their base forms. For example, the phrase "traces of leakage found" becomes "trace" and "leak," which allows more effective identification of relevant keywords. This ensures that variations in phrasing, such as "leaks" and "leak," do not affect analysis, maintaining consistency in identifying similar defects in records. At this stage, missing and noisy data are also processed, where records with missing details or ambiguous descriptions, if any, are flagged for verification or supplemented with standardized fillers. Additionally, expert comments that lack specifics are noted to minimize potential misclassification at later stages.

In NLP, tokenization is used at multiple levels (word, subword, and character). This helps to determine the most effective segmentation strategy for capturing technical language and terms related to the planning of preventive measures. To capture important information when processing inspection results, several methods are considered (**Table 3**).

The use of clustering methods allows the classification of inspection results into groups that reflect the severity of malfunctions and the condition of equipment, thus aiding in

prioritizing maintenance activities. For example, based on existing textual descriptions, the K-means method transforms inspection results into feature vectors. In the case of a valve, descriptors such as "seal failure," "leak," "corrosion," "wear" may appear in the inspection result descriptions.

Table 3. Characteristics of text representation methods.

Method	Characteristics
Bag of Words (BoW)	Each inspection result text is transformed into a vector based on the frequency of terms present in the text. For example, inspection result text for Valve 1 contains terms such as "tightness," "ring," and "liquid leakage." These terms form a feature set, registering the presence or absence of each word and frequency, which helps to identify patterns or common issues for multiple valves. If "tightness" is a frequent feature, it may indicate common problems with sealing in the inspected valves.
TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency)	To capture the significance of terms that are particularly informative, the TF-IDF method is used. Terms that occur frequently across all documents, such as common words for inspection results (e.g., "inspection," which can also mean checking, examining), are weighted lower, while specific terms related to defects, such as "leak" (liquid leak) and "tightness violation" (seal breakdown), are given higher weight in documents where they appear less frequently. In our example, terms like "liquid leak" and "violation" will have higher TF-IDF scores, reflecting their diagnostic importance.
Word Embedding	This method is used to capture semantic relationships between words. Words with similar meanings (e.g., "leak" and "leakage" for leaks) are embedded into a multidimensional space where they appear closer together. This is particularly valuable for synonyms or different terminology used in various inspection descriptions. For example, the embedding space might place terms related to tightness and liquid leakage near each other, indicating a shared context related to valve functionality. This approach helps our model generalize and detect relevant problems even if experts use different phrasing.
Named Entity Recognition (NER)	This method is used to extract key entities such as specific components and defect types from the text. For example, in a valve inspection, entities like "ring" and "liquid leakage" are identified and tagged, allowing the recognition of details and their conditions across multiple inspections. This enhances the model's ability to identify which specific components (e.g., rings, seals) are linked to recurring issues.
Topic Modeling	Topic modeling is applied to identify hidden themes or defect types in inspection texts. Using methods like Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), we identify clusters of terms related to common issues. For example, a topic may emerge around seal failures if terms like "leak," "tightness," and "seal" frequently appear in inspections. This allows grouping valves by types of reported problems, providing insight into common failure modes and helping prioritize preventive measures.

This method allows grouping similar features together so that equipment with similar issues (e.g., valve or compressor malfunctions due to sealing issues) can be serviced together because each cluster represents a common defect type or issue severity for all types of equipment. Hierarchical clustering can be used to organize inspection results into a defect taxonomy, starting with broad issues (e.g., "mechanical wear") and narrowing down to specific subtypes (e.g., minor wear – critical wear). For example, a high-level cluster may include "leak problems" observed across different types of equipment, with nested clusters differentiating between minor leaks (requiring monitoring) and critical leaks (requiring immediate intervention). This hierarchical organization supports the prioritization of maintenance actions based on the urgency of intervention, where critical issues are addressed immediately, and less severe cases are planned for subsequent scheduled inspections.

At the same time, the developed predictive model should rely not only on data obtained from inspection results but also consider the operating context, which plays a key role in accurately predicting maintenance needs. Let's consider the content of the operating conditions for valves as an example (**Table 4**).

Table 4. Example of valve operating conditions description.

Attribute	Description
Aggressiveness of the working environment	Characterizes the level of exposure to corrosive, abrasive, or other degrading conditions.
Criticality of failures	Characterizes the impact of equipment failure on production processes, labor safety, or potential environmental risks.
Age	Expressed in years, reflecting the cumulative effect of time on the integrity and performance of equipment.
Production downtime due to failures	Quantified in hours, highlighting past issues with the equipment and characterizing reliability.
Load	Number of operating cycles per month, reflecting the intensity of mechanical and operational loads.

Contextual data supplements the inspection results, offering a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing equipment condition. The operating context allows adapting recommendations to the unique conditions in which each piece of equipment operates. At the same time, some attributes may be missing significant features, so an important step in predictive modeling is feature engineering. This step plays a crucial role in ensuring that the model can effectively understand patterns and relationships in the data. For example, inspection result records and equipment operating context may contain implicit information that cannot be directly interpreted by machine learning models. Feature engineering allows extracting and highlighting this information, ensuring that the model receives input data not only in a structured but also meaningful form. Thus, in the valve example, raw data might be: "Inspection of valve No. 16 showed slight cracking of the gasket with no leakage," "Valve No. 16 is installed in a very aggressive environment." Engineered feature: object (valve), defect severity level (moderate), affected component (gasket),

environmental aggressiveness level (high). The resulting characteristics from the context of operating conditions and inspection results are combined into a unified representation of equipment condition information. Processed characteristics are fed into the model algorithm, which analyzes patterns and relationships in the data to generate recommendations. The model's output recommendations are considered in the planning of preventive measures aimed at enhancing equipment reliability and minimizing production downtime.

To assess the performance and effectiveness of the predictive model, a combination of quantitative and qualitative metrics is used (Table 5).

Table 5. Evaluation Metrics

Metric	Characteristics
Prediction Accuracy	Accuracy, recall, and F1-score metrics: used for comprehensive evaluation of classification of equipment issues into categories such as "requires immediate intervention," "requires monitoring," or "no action required." Accuracy evaluates the proportion of correctly predicted positive outcomes, recall evaluates the proportion of actual positive outcomes captured by the model, and the F1-score provides the harmonic mean of these two metrics.
	Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Squared Error (MSE): Used for numerical forecasts, such as the predicted time to failure or optimal maintenance intervals. These metrics measure the average deviation of predictions from actual values.
Contextual Relevance	Contextual relevance evaluation: assesses how well the model takes into account the operating context (e.g., environmental aggressiveness, load intensity) in its predictions. This includes comparing the model's output with expert assessments or operational performance indicators.
	Ranking Metrics: For prioritizing maintenance tasks, ranking metrics such as Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG) evaluate the quality of the ranked output.
Reliability	Cross-validation evaluations: includes k-fold cross-validation for assessing model performance on different subsets of data, ensuring good generalization across various contexts and equipment types.
	Out-of-Sample Performance: Evaluates the model's performance on equipment or operating conditions not present in the training dataset.
Operational Metrics	Reducing downtime: the reduction of unscheduled downtime achieved through the model's maintenance recommendations.
	Cost Savings: Quantifies the reduction in maintenance and repair expenses achieved through the implementation of a preventive maintenance strategy based on decision support, compared to traditional approaches.
	Task Compliance Rate: Evaluates how often maintenance specialists follow the recommendations provided by the model.

RESULTS

The developed model for planning equipment maintenance in an industrial company integrates data obtained from equipment inspections with its operating context. The primary focus is on processing the textual content of inspection results using natural language processing (NLP) methods, which allows extracting key defect and malfunction characteristics, as well as classifying them by importance and required actions in the context of equipment operation. During the experiments, the model was successfully tested on a dataset of valves at the studied enterprise, demonstrating the potential for scaling the approach to other types of equipment. The model shows accuracy and reliability of results sufficient for decision-making, as confirmed by the metrics. The results confirm the potential of the proposed model to improve the efficiency of the equipment maintenance system in enterprises, including reducing failure risks and optimizing operational processes.

DISCUSSION

The results obtained demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed model in the tasks of planning equipment maintenance. However, they require detailed analysis and critical reflection. The main advantage of the model lies in the integration of equipment inspection data and operational context, which allows considering the specific conditions in which the equipment operates. This approach shows significant potential for reducing failure rates and optimizing maintenance-related costs. However, despite the successful testing of the model on real data from the studied enterprise (the valve example), there are aspects that require further study, one of which is the limitation of the data, as using only inspection data restricts the completeness of the analysis. Although textual information and operational parameters (such as aggressiveness of the environment, criticality of failures, etc.) provide valuable insights, including sensor data and monitoring systems would improve the model's accuracy and versatility. This is especially important for dynamically changing operating conditions. The next aspect concerns the processing of textual data. The NLP methods applied to analyze inspection result descriptions have shown their effectiveness. However, the quality and volume of text provided by experts play a crucial role. Future research should focus on ways to improve the standardization of textual reports and their compliance with machine learning requirements. Moreover, despite the successful operation with valve analysis, there is a question about the applicability of the model to other types of equipment. Differences in the nature of defects, failure rates, and operating conditions may require the adaptation or revision of algorithms. The metrics used have proven their usefulness for model evaluation, but further work may be directed at developing additional metrics that would take into account the economic impact or influence on the enterprise's production indicators. Additionally, developing interfaces and visualization tools to simplify interpretation would be an important task.

Thus, the proposed model is a significant step forward in the development of intelligent decision-support systems for equipment maintenance. However, further work is required to address limitations and expand the model's applicability to ensure even higher levels of reliability and efficiency in production processes.

CONCLUSION

This paper discusses the approach to developing an intelligent decision-support system for preventive maintenance planning at a chemical industry enterprise. The focus is on creating a model that uses equipment inspection data to generate recommendations for planning maintenance activities. The developed method is based on the integration of modern natural language processing (NLP) techniques and machine learning. The analysis of inspection texts using NLP helped identify key indicators of equipment condition, while considering the operational context (such as the aggressiveness of the working environment, criticality of failures, equipment age, and usage intensity) ensured sufficient accuracy and adaptability of the model to the specifics of chemical production. However, during the work, issues were identified regarding text processing, including linguistic difficulties in tokenization and lemmatization. This highlights the need for further research in NLP to improve the processing of textual data in the Russian language, which is important for Russian-speaking enterprises. The presented work is a significant contribution to the development of preventive maintenance strategies and opens opportunities for further improvement, including expanding data sources, adapting the model for other types of equipment, and enhancing result interpretability.

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